

Strong stellar-driven outflows shape the evolution of galaxies at cosmic dawn

Fontanot, Hirschmann, De Lucia ApJL in press

Fabio Fontanot
Galaxy Evolution across time
Paris 16/06/17

Outline

- ◆ **New Semi-analytical Model of Galaxy Formation and Evolution**
- ◆ **GAEA**

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- ◆ **New Semi-analytical Model of Galaxy Formation and Evolution**
 - ◆ **GAEA**
- ◆ **Evolution of high-z galaxies**
 - ◆ **Critical test of stellar feedback**

GAlaxy **E**volution and **AA**ssembly

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<http://www.mpa-garching.mpg.de/millennium>

GAEA

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- ◆ Detailed Chemical Enrichment **De Lucia+14**

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 - ◆ No IRA
 - ◆ Explicit timescales for SNIa SNII and AGB stars

GAEA

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the method adopted to store the contributions from different types of stars in the future, and incorporate the metals in the baryonic gaseous phase of model galaxies during their evolution. The thick line shows the time interval between two subsequent snapshots. The two arrays at the top and at the bottom of the figure represent a ‘metal restitution array’ (RETURNEDMET) that is associated with each model galaxy and contains the mass of elements returned, at any time in the future, by the SSPs that constitute the model galaxy under consideration. At each time-step, the code computes the elements produced and adds them to the future bins (in case there is an episode of star formation), and then reads from the array RETURNEDMET the amount of metals that needs to be re-incorporated. The grey array shown in the figure is a ‘virtual array’ used to project metals in the appropriate bins.

DeLucia+14

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Hirschmann De Lucia & Fontanot 2016

GAEA

Hirschmann, De Lucia & Fontanot 2016 (see also Henriques+13 or White+14)

GAEA “Old” feedback schemes

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Ejective/Preventive feedback

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$$\dot{M}_{\text{reheat}} = \epsilon_{\text{reheat}} (1+z)^{1.25} \left(\frac{V_{\text{max}}}{60 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right)^{\alpha} \times \dot{M}_{\text{star}}$$

“FIRE” simulation suite
Muratov+15

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As in **Guo+11**

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- ♦ **Mass dependent reincorporation**

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Hirschmann De Lucia & Fontanot 2016
- ◆ Other projects

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 - ◆ HI content of DMHs **Zoldan+17**
 - ◆ Variable IMF **Fontanot+17a**

Properties of high- z galaxies

GAEA high-z runs

- ◆ **Different Feedback Schemes**
 - ◆ **FIDUCIAL** => standard scheme as in **De Lucia+04, +14**
 - ◆ **H16F** => strong stellar-driven winds **Hirschmann+16**

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◆ Different Dust Treatment

- ◆ No-Dust
- ◆ Standard dust prescription as in [De Lucia&Blaizot07](#) (see also [Charlot&Fall00](#))

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 - ◆ FIDUCIAL => standard scheme as in [De Lucia+04, +14](#)
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- ◆ **Different Dust Treatment**
 - ◆ No-Dust
 - ◆ Standard dust prescription as in [De Lucia&Blaizot07](#) (see also [Charlot&Fall00](#))
- ◆ **Reference simulations (different resolution)**
 - ◆ MS
 - ◆ MSII

Fontanot+17b

Nodust

Fontanot+17b

Fontanot+17b

Conclusions

- ◆ **Strong stellar-driven outflows coupled with mass-dependent re-accretion timescales are able to recover the evolution of the rest-frame UV and optical LFs over the redshift range $4 < z < 7$**
- ◆ **GAEA provides a self consistent picture of galaxy evolution at $z < 10$**
- ◆ **Beware Dust!**
 - ◆ **GAEA in qualitative agreement with UV-selected samples**
 - ◆ **Self-consistent models of dust still missing**
 - ◆ **Powerful discriminant between different stellar feedback schemes**